

Photometric and Light Curve Analysis of Supernova SN2025qpk

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Abstract

This study presents a photometric analysis of the supernova SN2025qpk using observational data obtained from the Las Cumbres Observatory (LCO) 1.0-meter Sinistro telescope network. The data were collected through multiple optical filters (B, V, and R) and processed using AstroImageJ to extract instrumental magnitudes and relative fluxes. The combined light curve includes data from multiple filters (B, V, R) to show the general brightness evolution of SN 2025qpk. Our analysis suggests that the peak brightness occurred on July 26, 2025. Assuming a typical Type Ia supernova absolute magnitude of -19.3 , we estimate the distance to the supernova to be approximately 1.88×10^8 light years (5.75×10^7 parsecs) using the distance modulus relation. Because the observation window was limited, the decline rate in magnitudes per day could not be reliably determined. Phase analysis shows that the observations were taken approximately 8.5 minutes before peak brightness, consistent with a near-maximum phase. After correction for the small redshift, the rest-frame phase difference remains effectively unchanged. This work demonstrates how photometry and basic light-curve analysis can be used to estimate distance, identify the brightness phase, and characterize the temporal evolution of a supernova, even with limited observational data.

1 Introduction

The explosion of a star is one of the most phenomenal activities in the universe. For the past several decades, astronomers and scientists have been exploring the ever-expanding universe by analyzing supernova explosions. Supernovae are cosmic recyclers, scattering building blocks of planets and life into space [7]. Among the different types of supernovae, Type Ia supernovae are of particular importance because they act as standard candles, objects with a known intrinsic brightness.

Scientists classify supernovae into two major types: Type I (Ia, Ib, Ic) and Type II (IIp, III, IIn). When a star explodes, the specific behavior of the star with its cause determines which type it is grouped into. A Type Ia supernova is an explosion that happens in a binary system, where two stars orbit each other. One of them is a dense remnant called a white dwarf. Over time, the white dwarf can steal mass from the other star, and when it reaches its maximum mass limit (the Chandrasekhar limit, $1.4M_{\odot}$), it explodes. Type Ia supernovae are known as standard candles to measure distance in the universe, and they don't contain hydrogen in their spectra.

Type Ib, Type Ic, and all Type II supernovae are all forms of core-collapse supernovae, meaning they mark the violent deaths of massive stars that run out of nuclear fuel and whose cores collapse under gravity. When the collapse happens, the outer layers of the star are blown off in a huge explosion. The key differences between these types depend on how much of the star's outer layers were lost before the explosion [5].

Another significant aspect of supernovae is how they evolve. Specifically, Type Ia supernovae achieve peak value and gradually decline. To study this, plotting the changes in magnitude over time becomes essential to studying the supernovae's properties and the parent star. A light curve, therefore, is a graph that plots the light intensity on the y-axis and the time on the x-axis [7].

The supernova SN2025qpk is located in the UGC 11622 emission-line galaxy, 170 million light-years away in the constellation Aquarius. The supernova was discovered on July 07, 2025, with a magnitude of 19.805 and declined to a magnitude of 14.5, consistent with a typical Type Ia supernova [1].

2 Methods

Data was collected from the Las Cumbres Observatory using the 1.0-meter Sinistro telescope. The dataset consisted of images taken using the B, V, and R filters. The images were pre-processed by the LCO pipeline, which performed bias subtraction, dark correction, and flat-fielding to remove instrumental effects. [8].

Figure 1: Raw LCO image of SN2025qpk taken through the V filter.

Figure 2: Reduced LCO image of SN2025qpk taken through the V filter.

The reduced FITS images were imported into AstroImageJ (AIJ) for photometric analysis. To identify the right target from our images, we took the coordinates(RA, DEC) and passed them through SIMBAD, and located our target.

Table 1: Target Information

Object	Type	RA	DEC	Host Galaxy	Filters Used
SN2025qpk	Type Ia SN	20:44:37.563	-01:43:12.51	UGC 11622	B, V, R

Figure 3: Image taken from SIMBAD showing the target.

Using AIJ's Multi-Aperture Photometry tool, circular apertures were placed on the supernova (target) and on several nearby comparison stars within the same field selected by AIJ automatically as good comparisons.

Figure 4: Green marker: target; red markers: comparison stars.

The photometric data were automatically compiled in the Measurements Table in AIJ, containing quantities such as Julian Date (JD-UTC), airmass, FWHM, source flux, and relative flux.

Label	Filter	Saturated	JD - 2400000	JD - UTC	JD - SCOPES	RAJ2000	DECJ2000	AIRMASS	ALT - DEG	CCD - TEMP	EXPTIME	FWHM - ARC	DECORRN	DECORRN	FWHM - Pixel
cpd=013-fw01	20250725-013a	0	60882.560907429	2460882.56090742	FWHM	0	1.43170112	FWHM	0	30	FWHM	FWHM	FWHM	FWHM	6.8860717011
cpd=013-fw02	20250725-013a	2	60882.5614980229	2460882.56149802	FWHM	0	1.42121096	FWHM	0	30	FWHM	FWHM	FWHM	FWHM	6.28692246176
cpd=013-fw03	20250725-013a	3	60882.5621239208	2460882.56212392	FWHM	0	1.42521113	FWHM	0	30	FWHM	FWHM	FWHM	FWHM	6.98975622485
cpd=013-fw04	20250725-013a	4	60882.5627948778	2460882.56279488	FWHM	0	1.42940209	FWHM	0	30	FWHM	FWHM	FWHM	FWHM	6.76889808848
cpd=013-fw05	20250725-013a	5	60882.5634663485	2460882.56346635	FWHM	0	1.43337326	FWHM	0	30	FWHM	FWHM	FWHM	FWHM	6.82316609585
cpd=013-fw06	20250725-013a	6	60882.5642273812	2460882.56422738	FWHM	0	1.43798371	FWHM	0	40	FWHM	FWHM	FWHM	FWHM	6.27575959272
cpd=013-fw07	20250725-013a	7	60882.5649889187	2460882.56498892	FWHM	0	1.44295071	FWHM	0	40	FWHM	FWHM	FWHM	FWHM	6.04891042673
cpd=013-fw08	20250725-013a	8	60882.5657426906	2460882.56574269	FWHM	0	1.44892507	FWHM	0	40	FWHM	FWHM	FWHM	FWHM	6.3979567506
cpd=013-fw09	20250725-013a	9	60882.5664993404	2460882.56649934	FWHM	0	1.45374237	FWHM	0	40	FWHM	FWHM	FWHM	FWHM	6.99593952108
cpd=013-fw10	20250725-013a	10	60882.5672562262	2460882.56725623	FWHM	0	1.4589494	FWHM	0	40	FWHM	FWHM	FWHM	FWHM	6.3064822208
cpd=013-fw11	20250725-013a	11	60882.5680137133	2460882.56801371	FWHM	0	1.4644166	FWHM	0	30	FWHM	FWHM	FWHM	FWHM	6.1827262519
cpd=013-fw12	20250725-013a	12	60882.5687691873	2460882.56876919	FWHM	0	1.4699342	FWHM	0	30	FWHM	FWHM	FWHM	FWHM	6.181878888
cpd=013-fw13	20250725-013a	13	60882.5695325754	2460882.56953258	FWHM	0	1.4734384	FWHM	0	28	FWHM	FWHM	FWHM	FWHM	6.1370728544
cpd=013-fw14	20250725-013a	14	60882.5702973108	2460882.57029731	FWHM	0	1.4779447	FWHM	0	30	FWHM	FWHM	FWHM	FWHM	6.70542029385
cpd=013-fw15	20250725-013a	15	60882.5706136796	2460882.57061368	FWHM	0	1.4826813	FWHM	0	30	FWHM	FWHM	FWHM	FWHM	6.5340486171

Figure 5: Measurements table from AIJ.

The Julian Dates were converted into standard calendar dates using NASA's JD Date/Time Converter for analysis [4]. Due to limitations of data on each filter, the light curve constructed was using the relative fluxes from the B, V, and R filters altogether, plotted against JD-UTC. This may not provide as much information as the light curves from each filter would give about the color evolution of the supernova, but the general trend of the light curve we got gives us important insights. We then took the measurements table from AIJ, opened it in LibreOffice Calc, and plotted the light curve manually.

Figure 6: Light curve of SN2025qpk combining B, V, and R filters.

3 Results

Photometric analysis of SN 2025qpk yielded relative fluxes in the B, V, and R filters, which were combined to construct the light curve shown in Figure 6. The light curve indicates the supernova reached its peak brightness on July 26, 2025. From this, we calculated the phase of the supernova, which indicates how far in time our observation is from the peak brightness. The time of observation of the target (t_{obs}) was on July 26, 2025, at 1:27:18 AM, and the peak brightness was at 1:35:46 AM. (taking the median Julian date value of our light curve). Then,

$$\text{Phase} = t_{\text{obs}} - t_{\text{peak}} = 5238 \text{ s} - 5746 \text{ s} = -508 \text{ s} \approx -8.5 \text{ minutes} \approx -0.00579 \text{ days}$$

The negative value indicates the SN was observed approximately 8.5 minutes before the supernova reached its peak brightness. Since our SN is distant, we corrected the phase for time dilation using the red shift (z), $z = 0.013881$ [6]

$$\text{Phase}_{\text{rest}} = \frac{\text{phase}_{\text{obs}}}{1 + z}$$

$$\text{Phase}_{\text{rest}} = \frac{-0.00587}{1 + 0.013881} = -0.00579 \text{ days}$$

The value we obtain here is approximately the same as the one we obtained above (-0.00587756 days). This can be attributed to the fact that the redshift is so small, therefore, time dilation. We couldn't find a good comparison star to calculate the apparent magnitude of our target, so instead, we used an already provided apparent magnitude of the supernova as of July 25, 2025 [1], and calculated its distance using the distance modulus.[8] We know that the absolute magnitude of a type Ia supernova is -19.3. The apparent magnitude ($m = 14.5$) and absolute magnitude ($M = -19.3$) give:

$$m - M = 5 \log_{10}(d) - 5$$

M is the absolute magnitude, while m is the apparent magnitude. $m = 14.5$, $M = -19.3$.

$$14.5 - (-19.3) = 5 \log_{10}(d) - 5$$

$$38.8 = 5 \log_{10}(d)$$

$$d = 1.88 \times 10^8 \text{ light-years } (5.75 \times 10^7 \text{ parsecs}) (1 \text{ parsec} = 3.26 \text{ light years})$$

4 Discussion

The constructed light curve of SN 2025qpk (Figure 6) shows a brightness peak around July 26, 2025. The estimated apparent magnitude ($m = 14.5$) combined with the standard absolute magnitude of a Type Ia supernova ($M = -19.3$) yields a distance of approximately 1.88×10^8 light-years (5.75×10^7 parsecs). Phase analysis indicates

that the observations were taken just before the maximum light, approximately 8.5 minutes before peak brightness. This timing provides valuable information about the pre-maximum phase of the supernova, a period that is rarely observed. The small redshift correction ($z = 0.013881$) did not significantly alter the phase, confirming that relativistic time dilation effects are negligible for supernovae at such low redshifts. We combined data from all filters into a single light curve, which represents a brightness trend, but not a monochromatic light curve, adding uncertainty to the shape and peak timing.

The limited time of observation near peak brightness restricts our ability to determine the decline rate ($\frac{\Delta\text{mag}}{\Delta t}$) and model the full light curve. During data collection, we did not calculate the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) to choose exposure time, which may introduce additional uncertainty in the photometric results. In future supernova projects, we will ensure a longer observational window to collect more comprehensive data and use Python codes to give us more reliable outcomes regarding the selection of comparison stars and plotting the light curve. Despite these limitations, the overall behavior of the light curve remains consistent with expectations for a Type Ia supernova.

5 Conclusion

This study analyzed Supernova 2025qpk using multi-filter photometry (B, V, R) from the Las Cumbres Observatory 1.0-meter Sinistro telescope. The observations captured the supernova approximately 8.5 minutes before peak brightness, allowing determination of its near-maximum phase. Using the apparent magnitude $m = 14.5$ and a standard Type Ia absolute magnitude $M = -19.3$, the distance to SN 2025qpk was estimated as $d = 1.88 \times 10^8$ light-years (5.75×10^7 parsecs).

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